

FORMATION OF TOTAL ROOT WEIGHT IN PLANTS OF RIDGES AND FAMILIES OBTAINED BY COMPLEX HYBRIDIZATION

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Annotation: In the article, according to the results of the research, it is shown that the total root weight indicators change in different degrees in all ridges and families in drought conditions compared to the option of optimal water supply.

Keywords: the formation of the total root weight, the model variety, family, ridge, plants.

Introduction: The study of root systems is important in classifying the physiological characteristics of plants. The degree of water supply to cotton alters the variation of the root system. This change ensures the development of the underground part of the cotton.

According to the research results of our scientists, it was observed that the total root weight increases in different degrees all genotypes in drought conditions compared to the option of optimal water supply [2; p. 68]. In our research, along with the important physiological indicators of cotton, the total root weight of the plants during the ripening period was analyzed by measuring the total root weight of the rows and families selected in the optimal irrigation system (1-2-1) and under water deficit (0-1-0) conditions. In our study, in non-saline soil and climatic conditions, in an optimal irrigation system, it was observed that the highest indicators of the total root weight indicator were observed in the O-17-19 family (140.5 g) among the isolated families during gross ripening period, i.e., during harvest, while the lowest indicator of total root weight among families is in O-12-15 (133.5 g) family (see Table 1). In S-6524 and An-Boyovut-2 varieties, which participated as model varieties, this indicator was 134.2, 138.5 g, respectively. In water-scarce conditions, the total root weight in families was formed on average in

the range of 117.4-124.7 g, while in the isolated T-14-16/14 ridge, this indicator was 120.2 g, and in S-6524 and An-Boyovut-2 varieties, which participated as a sample, this indicator was in the range of 115.9-127.1 g, respectively. It was observed that the total root weight in the isolated families under saline soil conditions and optimal irrigation system was 131.2-138.6 g on average, 139.2 g in the T-14-16/14 range, and in S-6524 and An-Boyovut-2 varieties, which participated as a sample variety, it was 136.1 and 137.9 g, respectively. In water shortage conditions, the roots of all family, ridge and pattern varieties appeared less developed than the roots of the analyzed family, ridge and pattern varieties under optimal irrigation system.

Table 1

Formation of the total root weight of plants of model varieties, ridges and families (g)

Family, ridge and model varieties	Non-saline soil conditions (Tashkent)		Saline soil conditions (Syr Darya)	
	optimal watering	water shortage	optimal watering	water shortage
2016 year				
O-95-96	133,7±2,1	118,2±1,8	131,5±2,7	116,7±2,7
O-23-24	139,2±2,8	124,8±1,6	137,8±2,2	121,5±2,5
O-97-99	136,1±1,9	117,4±2,3	135,6±2,6	116,9±2,6
O-10-11	140,4±1,9	121,3±2,7	136,2±2,4	120,8±2,2
O-12-14	133,5±1,8	119,2±3,1	131,2±2,3	117,5±2,4
O-17-19	140,5±2,1	122,3±2,9	138,6±2,5	120,0±3,2
T-14-16/14	141,1±1,6	120,2±2,4	139,2±2,1	121,4±2,7

C-6524	134,2±1,8	115,9±2,2	136,1±1,6	116,2±2,4
An-Boyovut-2	138,5±1,4	127,1±2,8	137,9±1,9	125,4±2,1
2017 year				
O-95-96	139,4±3,5	125,3±3,1	136,1±3,5	122,7±2,4
O-23-24	136,5±2,9	119,5±3,5	134,9±2,9	116,1±2,7
O-97-99	138,8±2,7	120,4±2,7	135,2±2,7	119,9±1,3
O-10-11	140,8±3,6	125,6±3,3	138,3±3,6	123,4±3,5
O-12-14	132,7±2,5	117,2±2,9	130,5±2,5	115,7±3,4
O-17-19	134,1±2,8	119,1±3,0	131,8±2,8	116,8±3,2
T-14-16/14	141,5±1,8	122,3±3,3	138,6±1,8	121,9±2,7
C-6524	139,1±1,9	131,5±2,6	132,7±1,9	129,8±2,5
An-Boyovut-2	137,6±2,6	128,2±2,9	135,1±2,6	126,1±2,6
2018 year				
O-95-96	141,7±2,9	127,7±2,2	138,5±1,7	125,5±2,8
O-23-24	140,8±3,0	123,3±3,4	136,7±3,1	120,8±3,0
O-97-99	133,4±2,8	119,1±2,8	135,1±2,4	117,4±2,6
O-10-11	151,3±2,3	122,6±2,6	143,5±2,9	123,5±2,9
O-12-14	149,4±2,1	120,4±2,7	145,7±2,7	122,2±2,8
O-17-19	136,6±3,0	117,7±3,0	134,2±3,3	119,1±2,2
T-14-16/14	137,9±2,1	122,1±2,5	135,4±2,3	120,2±2,7
C-6524	133,4±2,2	119,5±2,4	130,6±2,6	116,1±2,5
An-Boyovut-2	139,5±2,7	125,4±2,1	135,1±2,5	123,2±2,3

In the researches of P.Sh. Ibragimov [1; 23-25 p.] and other researchers it has been shown that inter-hybrid complex crossbreeding in cotton leads to wide variability in terms of value-agricultural traits, and it allows the selection of transgressive genotypes, where the greatest variability is observed in combinations involving hybrids with high constants of specific combinative ability, as a result of which it is possible to distinguish lines with fast ripening, high yield and high fiber quality. It should be noted that genetically enriched forms, lines and varieties of various agricultural crops have been created on the basis of complex cross-breeding.

In the second year of research, the total root weight during the ripening period of the plants of the family formed 132.7-140.8 g on average in the optimal irrigation (1-2-1) system, while it was 141.5 g in the plants of the T-14-16/14 ridge. The roots of the S-6524 and An-Boyovut-2 varieties, which participated in the research as a model variety, were 139.1-137.6 g, respectively, in the optimal irrigation (1-2-1) system, the roots of the plants of the T-14-16/14 ridge are somewhat stronger than the roots of the model varieties and families. The roots of the families under water shortage conditions were on average 117.2-125.6 g, and it was shown that it was 20-30 g lower than the roots of the analyzed families under optimal irrigation system. In these conditions, the S-6524 and An-Boyovut-2 varieties, which participated as a model variety, were 131.5 and 128.6 g, respectively. It was observed that even in the conditions of saline soils, the roots of the analyzed families planted in an optimal irrigation system were slightly higher than the traces of the analyzed families under water scarcity conditions. D.G'. Jones [3; p. 207] states that one of the effective methods of selection is the double hybridization method, which makes it possible to obtain recombinants with high productivity. They will have a wider variability than ordinary hybrids. But this variability is mainly manifested in the increase in the ability of plants to adapt. According to the results of the research carried out by M. Tojiev, G.A. Kurbanova, K. Tadjiev [4; 22-24-p.], it can be observed that irrigation rates have different effects on the growth, development and yield of cotton.

In the third year of our research, under non-saline soil climatic conditions, optimal irrigation system, the highest index of total root weight of plants was observed in the O-10-11 family (149.4 g), while the lowest index was recorded in the O-97-99 family (133.4 g). In the S-6524 and An-Boyovut-2 varieties, which participated in the experiments as a model variety, this indicator was 133.4 and 139.5 g, respectively, and in the T-14-16/14 range it was 137.9 g. It was observed that the total root weight was formed in the average range of 117.7-127.7 g in the families isolated under water scarcity conditions, and it was 9.9-15.7 g less than the roots of the plants in the optimal irrigation system. Root weight was 119.5-125.4 g in sample S-6524 and An-Boyovut-2 varieties, respectively. In the conditions of saline soils, in the optimal irrigation system, the total root weight indicator of plants in families was formed in the range of 134.2-145.2 g on average, it was noted that this indicator was 135.4 g in the T-14-16-14 range, and 130.6-131.5 g in the S-6524 and An-Boyovut-2 varieties, which participated as a sample variety. Under water shortage conditions, the total root weight of the plants of the families was formed in the range of 117.4-125.5 g on average, and this indicator was 120.2 g on average in the T-14-16/14 range, and in S-6524 and An-Boyovut-2 varieties, which participated as a sample variety, it was 116.1 and 122.7 g, respectively.

Conclusion: Based on the data presented above, it can be concluded that our research showed that the total root weight indicators decrease in different degrees in all lines and families under drought conditions compared to the option of optimal water supply.

Our results obtained in these plants on the sign of total root weight show that the adaptation of plants to water deficit occurs due to various elements of the photosynthetic apparatus, including rapid ripening, changes in plant height and leaf thickness, in this regard, carrying out selection works will be highly effective.

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